

Influence of clinical and cerebral hemodynamics characteristics in acute ischemic stroke patients

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Abstract— This study investigated the relationship between clinical and hemodynamic aspects in acute ischemic stroke (AIS) patients and their impact on functional outcomes. Demographic, clinical, and hemodynamic data were collected from two clinical centers, comprising a total of 60 AIS patients and 50 control subjects. Stroke severity was assessed using the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) and functional outcome was assessed using modified Rankin Scale (mRS). Data on the history of atrial fibrillation, diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia and systemic arterial hypertension were collected. Arterial blood pressure (ABP) and cerebral blood flow velocity were recorded and Cerebral autoregulation was evaluated using the Autoregulation Index (ARI). Significant differences were observed in mRS scores among stroke subgroups (mild, moderate and severe), with severe stroke patients displaying worse functional outcomes (mRS = 3.5 ± 2.0) compared to mild (mRS = 0.8 ± 0.6) and moderate (mRS = 2.4 ± 1.2). Hemodynamic analysis revealed lower arterial blood pressure (ABP) in controls compared to AIS groups, while ARI values were significantly lower in severe stroke patients, suggesting impaired autoregulation. Strong positive correlations were found between NIHSS and mRS scores (0.83), as well as significant correlations between NIHSS and time from onset to assessment (0.73), mRS and time from onset to assessment (0.69), and atrial fibrillation (AF) and diabetes mellitus (DM) (0.65). Functional recovery (mRS) was significantly associated with stroke severity (NIHSS) ($p < 0.001$), with NIHSS scores predicting 71.2% of the variability in functional recovery. Hypercholesterolemia (HCL) was found to significantly influence functional recovery ($p = 0.02$). These findings highlight the importance of stroke severity assessment in predicting functional outcomes and underscore the potential role of cerebral autoregulation and comorbidities in influencing stroke severity and recovery. Understanding the interplay between clinical and hemodynamic factors in AIS can guide personalized treatment strategies and improve stroke care. Further research is needed to elucidate the underlying hemodynamic mechanisms and explore additional predictors of functional outcomes in AIS patients.

Keywords — Cerebral hemodynamics, acute ischemic stroke, cerebral autoregulation, clinical aspects

I. Introduction

Ischemic stroke is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide [1]. This disease presents significant

challenges to healthcare systems, and currently there is a crucial need to improve the actual understanding of its fundamental mechanisms, for a better therapeutic strategy [1].

The clinical and hemodynamic aspects of ischemic stroke play key roles in determining patient outcomes and guiding treatment decisions. Investigating these aspects provides valuable insights into the pathophysiology, prognosis, and management of this debilitating condition [2].

Clinically, ischemic stroke manifests as a sudden loss of blood flow to the brain, leading to a wide spectrum of neurological deficits that range from mild to severe [1]. Prompt and accurate assessment of stroke severity is essential for risk stratification, optimal resource allocation, and tailoring therapeutic interventions to individual patients [1].

The National Institutes of Heart Stroke Scale (NIHSS) is a systematic, quantitative assessment tool to measure stroke-related neurological deficit used to evaluate neurological status in acute stroke patients [3]. NIHSS is widely used to determine the severity of the stroke [3]. Accurate assessment of stroke severity facilitates the timely initiation of reperfusion therapies such as intravenous thrombolysis and mechanical thrombectomy, known to improve clinical outcomes when administered within a critical time window [3].

Furthermore, modified Rankin Scale (mRS) is an essential instrument for measuring functional outcomes in stroke patients [4]. It allows classifying patients across the different disability levels and helps to evaluate the long-term impact of stroke on patients' quality of life and independence [4]. Understanding the relationship between clinical severity assessed by NIHSS and functional outcomes measured by mRS can aid in predicting patient outcomes and optimizing rehabilitation strategies [3].

In addition to clinical aspects, hemodynamic factors play a crucial role in ischemic stroke pathophysiology. Cerebral blood flow (CBF) regulation is a complex interplay between systemic blood pressure and cerebral autoregulation [4]. Impaired CBF and perfusion deficits in the ischemic penumbra can determine whether the brain tissue will recover or be irreversibly damaged, making hemodynamic assessment essential in identifying brain tissue that could be preserved from further damage or death if detected and treated promptly and guiding treatment decisions [2].

Transcranial Doppler ultrasound is a valuable tool to measure CBF velocity (CBFv) in the middle cerebral artery, providing valuable information about cerebral perfusion status in stroke patients [2]. Moreover, understanding the interplay between hemodynamic parameters, such as arterial blood pressure (ABP), cerebral autoregulation (CA), and heart rate, can elucidate the risk factors and potential triggers for ischemic stroke [2].

This study represents the first investigation of cerebral hemodynamic aspects in acute ischemic stroke (AIS) using data from two distinct clinical centers, encompassing a total of 110 patients (60 AIS and 50 control participants). Investigating the clinical severity, functional outcomes, and hemodynamic status of AIS patients, we would be able in future optimize treatment strategies, identify potential therapeutic targets, and ultimately work towards reducing the burden of AIS on individuals and societies.

II. Material and Methods

A. Research Participants

In this study, we included patients from two clinical centers to explore and analyze the research objectives.

Data of 34 consecutive patients with AIS and data of 12 control participants were collected at Hospital das Clínicas in São Paulo, Brazil. The study received approval from the local ethics committee of the University of São Paulo (approval number 982.280) and was conducted in compliance with the principles outlined in the declaration of Helsinki. All patients and their relatives provided written informed consent to participate.

Eligible patients met the following criteria: first-ever AIS within 48 hours of onset and identifiable signs of focal neurological dysfunction in the middle cerebral artery (MCA) with or without MCA stenosis. Exclusion criteria included: (1) presence of intracranial or subarachnoid hemorrhage on Computed Tomography (CT) or Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), (2) other significant intracranial or extracranial major vascular stenosis or occlusion (assessed by transcranial Doppler ultrasound and transcranial color-coded duplex sonography, respectively), (3) absence of sufficient temporal bone window for MCA insonation, and (4) history of myocardial infarction within the last six months or other neurological disorders. Patients with impaired consciousness, inability to cooperate sufficiently for the hemodynamic assessment, or insufficient quality of hemodynamic recordings were also excluded. Age- and sex-matched healthy control subjects were recruited from the Department staff, relatives of recruited patients, and researchers. Control subjects were excluded if they had a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack, diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, carotid artery stenosis, or had smoked within the last five years.

From the second center, data of 26 AIS and 38 control participants were collected. Participants were recruited from consecutive patients admitted to the Stroke Unit at the Leicester Royal Infirmary (University Hospitals of Leicester NHS Trust) after a first ever episode of ischemic stroke within 48 hours of symptoms onset. The Nottingham Research Ethics Committee 1, UK approved the research protocol (ref.: 11/EM/0016), all study subjects gave informed consent. For patients waking with a stroke, time of onset was taken to be the

time when the patient was last asymptomatic. Neurological examinations were conducted immediately before transcranial Doppler ultrasound recording. Only right-handed healthy controls were recruited in the study. In both patients and controls group, handedness was established by means of the Edinburgh Inventory [4].

B. Clinical assessment

AIS was defined as the occurrence of stroke confirmed by imaging (CT or MRI) and clinical diagnosis by a neurologist, blinded to cerebral hemodynamic analysis. NIHSS score was assessed at admission: ≤ 4 defining mild stroke, 5–15 moderate and ≥ 16 severe [3].

C. Clinical outcome

All participants were followed up at three months by a trained neurologist. Data on deaths, vascular events, ABP and mRS score were recorded. Poor functional outcome was defined as mRS > 2 .

D. Cerebral hemodynamic measurements

The investigator who performed the cerebral hemodynamic exams and analysis was blinded to admission clinical examination, including NIHSS score. Recordings (CBFv and ABP) for each subject were performed as described above. The study was conducted in a quiet research laboratory with participants lying in a comfortable supine position. CBFv in the MCA was continuously assessed by transcranial Doppler ultrasound (Viasys Companion III; Viasys Healthcare) using a dual 2-MHz transducer fitted to a head frame. ABP and heart rate were continuously recorded by a Finapres device (Ohmeda 2300; Finapres, Louisville, Colo., USA). All participants had abstained from caffeine, alcohol and nicotine for 2 h before the measurement. After 15 min of stabilization, a 5-min baseline recording was taken.

To assess CA, the Autoregulation index (ARI) was used. ARI is composed of 10 levels, ranging from damaged (ARI = 0) to intact (ARI = 9) CA. To calculate the ARI, a second-order differential equation was employed to simulate 10 sets of CBFv responses to an ideal step change in ABP. By comparing the recorded CBFv with the 10 simulated velocities, the ARI value was assigned to each subject for both hemispheres, using the best least squares error fit (i.e. lowest error between the subject ARI curve and the simulated velocities). This index has been previously applied in studies with stroke patients, proving to be efficient in differentiating the outcomes according to stroke severity [5].

E. Statistical analysis

To examine the impact of stroke severity on hemodynamics, patients were categorized into groups based on the admission NIHSS scores (mild, moderate, and severe). Subsequently, all systemic cerebral hemodynamic parameters were compared among these groups, using the control group as a reference.

Baseline demographics were compared among the four groups (mild, moderate, severe stroke, and controls) and baseline hemodynamics (ABP systolic and diastolic and heart rate) using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

TABLE 1. Clinical characteristics of AIS and control subjects

Clinical variables	AIS N=48			Control N = 45
	Mild N = 15 (31.2%)	Moderate N = 30 (62.5%)	Severe N= 3 (6.3%)	
Age, years (Mean \pm SD)	64.8 \pm 9.94	63.2 \pm 9.57	63.1 \pm 7.22	64.6 \pm 7.76
Male (%)	12 (60)	18 (37)	4 (67)	28 (42)
Hypertension	8 (40%)	24 (49%)	4 (67%)	-
Diabetes Mellitus	2 (10%)	16 (33%)	2 (33%)	-
Hypercholesterolaemia	2 (10%)	8 (16%)	2 (33%)	-
Atrial Fibrillation	-	8 (16%)	2 (33%)	-
Onset to assessment, hours	29.2 \pm 8.3	31.7 \pm 9.1	38.9 \pm 6.9	-
NIHSS	2.9 \pm 1.1	8.6 \pm 2.5	18.6 \pm 2.7	-
mRS	0.8 \pm 0.6	2.4 \pm 1.2	3.5 \pm 2.0	-

Bilateral CBFv and ARI were compared using two-factor mixed-design ANOVA with subject group as the between factor, and side of recording (right, left, affected and unaffected cerebral hemispheres) as the within factor.

Spearman's rho correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the relationship between clinical variables, such as stroke severity (admission NIHSS), functional outcome (three-month mRS), and history of systemic arterial hypertension (SAH), Hypercholesteremia (HCL), diabetes Mellitus (DM) and atrial fibrillation (AF). As considered by Muraka et al. [6], a correlation > 0.7 is classified as strong, [0.5 and 0.7] as moderate, and < 0.5 as weak. Linear regression analysis was performed to determine if good functional recovery (mRS ≤ 2) is independently associated with stroke severity based on NIHSS, and evaluate SAH, HCL, DM and AF as influence factors. Variables with values of $p < 0.05$ on univariate testing were included in this model. The measurement data are expressed as mean \pm SD, and the categorical data are expressed as the rate (percentage). P-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

III. Results

12 stroke and 5 control participants were excluded due to poor insonation of the temporal windows. Therefore, a total of 48 AIS subjects and 45 controls underwent data collection.

In the control group, there were no significant differences between the right and left cerebral hemispheres in terms of CBFv. Therefore, the average value for both hemispheres was utilized for further analyses.

Demographic and clinical characteristics were similar among stroke subgroups (Table 1). Significantly higher mRS scores were seen in the severe stroke group compared to mild and moderate groups (0.8 ± 0.6 , 2.4 ± 1.2 and 3.5 ± 2.0 , respectively).

Hemodynamic data are presented in Table 2. Significant lower ABP systolic and diastolic were seen in controls compared with the other three groups (AIS mild, moderate and severe), with $p < 0.05$. Moreover, no differences between groups in heart rate or in bilateral CBFv rate were found. ARI presented significant lower values in AIS severe group for affected and unaffected cerebral hemispheres when compared with controls ($p < 0.05$).

Correlations between clinical variables are presented in Figure 1A. NIHSS and mRS presented the strongest correlation between all the comparisons ($\rho = 0.83$). Most comparisons presented significant correlations, however, only correlations between NIHSS and mRS (0.83), NIHSS and Onset to assessment (0.73), presented strong correlations. Comorbidities presented only moderate to poor correlation with NIHSS and mRS.

TABLE 2. Hemodynamic characteristics of AIS and control subjects

Variables	AIS N=48			Control N = 45
	Mild N = 15 (31.2%)	Moderate N = 30 (62.5%)	Severe N= 3 (6.3%)	
Systolic ABP, mmHg	157.6 \pm 17.5	157.4 \pm 14.0	166.0 \pm 12.47	101.0 \pm 46.5*
Diastolic ABP, mmHg	86.5 \pm 20.4	90.7 \pm 7.99	93.8 \pm 5.1	62.7 \pm 12.2*
Heart rate, bpm	67.8 \pm 15.5	67.2 \pm 12.5	70.9 \pm 6.2	62.4 \pm 3.3
CBFv left hem., cm/s	-	-	-	51.1 \pm 3.6
	Affected hemisphere	44.5 \pm 13.1	47.7 \pm 16.0	37.9 \pm 25.2
	Unaffected hemisphere	50.7 \pm 9.5	49.0 \pm 26.2	66.3 \pm 21.9
CBFv right hem., cm/s	-	-	-	51.6 \pm 3.9
	Affected hemisphere	39.4 \pm 16.0	46.4 \pm 21.3	59.3 \pm 35.4
	Unaffected hemisphere	43.9 \pm 9.1	55.1 \pm 22.4	36.4 \pm 23.4
ARI	-	-	-	5.66 \pm 2.07 ^e
	Affected hemisphere	4.18 \pm 3.11	4.47 \pm 2.69	3.35 \pm 2.16
	Unaffected hemisphere	4.68 \pm 2.83	5.24 \pm 2.08	3.24 \pm 1.55

* $p < 0.05$ for post hoc Tukey for difference between control group and the other groups (AIS mild, moderate and severe). ^e $p < 0.05$ for post hoc Tukey for difference between control group and the AIS severe in Affected and Unaffected hemisphere.

Functional recovery (mRS) was associated with increasing stroke severity (NIHSS) (Figure 1B), with $R^2 = 0.712$ ($p < 0.001$), i.e., NIHSS can predict 71.2% of the functional recovery. Comorbidities (SAH, HCL, DM and AF) were evaluated in the model as predictor factors, but only HCL presented a significant influence in the model ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 1. A) Pearson correlation coefficients of clinical variables. B) Linear regression with mRS as dependent variable and NIHSS as independent variable. R: correlation coefficient. R^2 : coefficient of determination.

IV. Discussion

The present study investigated the demographic, clinical and hemodynamic characteristics of stroke subgroups and possible associations between the variables involved.

By combining patient data from multiple centers, the study enhances the generalizability and robustness of our findings, shedding light on the influence of clinical and hemodynamic factors in AIS.

The results demonstrated that the severity of stroke, as assessed by mRS, is significantly associated with functional disability. Patients with severe stroke exhibited considerably higher mRS scores compared to those with mild and moderate strokes, indicating worse functional outcomes for this subgroup.

Regarding hemodynamic parameters, the analysis revealed that controls have significantly lower systolic and diastolic ABP compared to all three stroke subgroups (mild, moderate and severe). However, no significant differences were observed between groups in heart rate or bilateral CBFv. These findings suggest that changes in ABP might be associated with the occurrence of stroke.

In line with previous studies [7], CA, assessed using ARI index, showed significantly lower values in the severe stroke group for both affected and unaffected cerebral hemispheres, as compared to controls. This indicates impaired autoregulation in severe stroke patients, which might contribute to the severity of neurological deficits observed in these individuals.

The results presented in this study add to existing evidence that cerebral hemodynamics are negatively affected in stroke patients, with increasing stroke severity leading to greater CA impairment [5]. Despite the results being in line with the expectation of finding impaired autoregulation in patients with severe stroke, the study has a low number of patients within this group, comprising only 3 patients out of the total of 48 studied, representing a limitation in this study. Therefore, for more robust conclusions, it would be advisable to conduct further studies with a larger population of severe stroke patients.

The correlation analysis revealed a strong and positive association between NIHSS and mRS, indicating that the severity of neurological impairment, as measured by NIHSS, is closely related to functional disability. Furthermore, significant correlations were also found between NIHSS and the time from symptoms onset to assessment, mRS and time from onset to assessment. These correlations suggest that prompt assessment and treatment initiation may play a crucial role in determining functional outcomes in stroke patients.

In line with this, the regression analysis demonstrated that stroke severity, significantly predicted functional recovery, with a considerable R -squared value of 0.712, indicating that 71.2% of the variance in functional recovery can be explained by NIHSS scores. Among the evaluated comorbidities, HCL emerged as a significant predictor of functional recovery, while other comorbidities did not exert a significant influence in the model.

Contrary to expectations, comorbidities exhibited a low correlation with the level of stroke severity and did not exert any influence within the linear regression model. This may have occurred due to participants with comorbidities constitute a small proportion compared to the total number of AIS participants studied (26.7%), especially the AF, that is present only in 13% of AIS participants. For more robust conclusions, a study with a larger number of AIS subjects with comorbidities is recommended.

V. Conclusion

These results emphasize the importance of stroke severity assessment in predicting functional outcomes and highlight the potential role of CA and hemodynamic factors in influencing stroke severity and recovery. Future studies should further investigate the underlying hemodynamic mechanisms and explore additional predictors of functional outcomes to develop personalized approaches to stroke management and rehabilitation.

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